

THE UNSTEADY DISCRETE ADJOINT METHOD FOR TURBOMACHINERY APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The unsteady discrete adjoint method for the calculation of objective function gradients for transient turbomachinery compressible viscous flows is presented. The URANS state equations are used along with the one-equation Spalart-Allmaras model. The implementation relies on an existing unsteady three-dimensional unstructured grid solver and discrete adjoint capabilities previously developed for steady flows. The formulation of the adjoint equations is introduced within a generic time-dependent CFD optimal design problem. An adjoint sliding plane functionality is also presented in order to enable multi-row time-dependent adjoint calculations, exploiting the rotor-stator interface. Algorithmic Differentiation (AD) is used to compute differential terms. Two testcases, a turbine vane and a turbine stage, are selected to demonstrate the feasibility of the method.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of the adjoint method (both discrete and continuous) [1, 2, 3, 4, 5] is well established in the field of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) for optimal design problems. In optimization problems, the sensitivity derivatives of a number of objective functions with respect to a number of inputs (design variables) is needed for gradient-based optimization algorithms. Conventional finite difference methods [6] suffer from step-size limitations and involve a computational cost that grows linearly with the number of design variables. Forward differentiation methods [7] overcome the step-size obstacle but still exhibit the high computational cost.

The adjoint method allows obtaining these sensitivities with a cost which is only proportional to the number

of objectives and essentially independent of the number of design variables. The fact that in many CFD-based optimization tasks the number of objectives and constraints is significantly smaller (quite often a few orders of magnitude) compared to the number of design variables makes the adjoint method quite popular in this field.

Despite the fact that the method has been used heavily for time-independent (steady) problems, its usage for time-dependent (unsteady) flows is still quite limited, see for example [9, 11]. In the field of turbomachinery unsteady flows the authors are only aware of the work of He [10] where the adjoint version of a nonlinear harmonic balance solver is employed to optimize the aeroelastic behaviour of rotor blades.

Due to the continuous advances in High Performance Computing (HPC), time-accurate simulation of the inherently unsteady turbomachinery flows is now becoming feasible for industrial problem sizes in project-relevant time scales. Therefore the extension of the adjoint method from steady to unsteady turbomachinery CFD models is needed to extend its benefits into the unsteady domain.

In this paper, a mathematical overview of the unsteady adjoint equations and some details of its implementation into a CFD solver are provided. Note that in contrast to [10], in this paper, the adjoint method is formulated and solved in the time domain. In addition, a method is proposed for handling rotor-stator interaction, thus allowing multi-row calculations. Finally, the method is applied to two turbomachinery testcases.

2 FORMULATING THE UNSTEADY ADJOINT SYSTEM

The state equations of the primal (non-linear) problem consist of:

- 1 equation for mass conservation
- 3 equations (x,y,z) for momentum conservation
- 1 equation for energy conservation
- 1 equation for turbulence modeling (Spalart-Allmaras [20] including wall functions is used in this work).

The aforementioned equations form the well-known Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) system and can be written as

$$R(Q, X) = 0, \quad (1)$$

where Q is the flow vector,

$$Q = [\rho \quad u \quad v \quad w \quad p \quad \tilde{\nu}]^T, \quad (2)$$

which contains density, the three components of velocity, pressure and the Spalart variable respectively. X denotes the mesh points coordinate matrix. The mesh is generated using the initial geometry, which is defined by the design variables α . This process can be represented by the mesh residual equation

$$R_m(\alpha, X) = 0. \quad (3)$$

In order to expand eq. (1) for unsteady flows (URANS), we need to add the volume-weighted time derivative of the flow, thus getting the unsteady flow residual

$$G(Q, X, t) = V \frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} + R(Q, X) = 0. \quad (4)$$

It should be noted that in this paper the mesh will not be treated as deforming, so X is a constant matrix, apart from the rigid mesh movement due to rotation (rotor-stator interaction), whose details and treatment can be found in section 4.

In order to solve eq. (4), the discretization of both space and time domain are needed. The spacial discretization is represented by the generated mesh X together with a 2nd order accurate method, see [17] for details. For the time discretization, we employ a backwards-difference formula (BDF) of 2nd order accuracy. The time step will be denoted by n . Thus the equation (4) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} & G(Q^n, Q^{n-1}, Q^{n-2}, X) = \\ & = V \frac{3Q^n - 4Q^{n-1} + Q^{n-2}}{2\Delta t} + R(Q^n, X) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The equation system (5) is solved iteratively for Q^n using

$$Q_{m+1}^n = Q_m^n + \Delta Q, \quad (6)$$

where m denotes the pseudo-time-stepping towards convergence of the steady problem per time step. By

substituting eq. (6) to eq. (5) and using a Taylor expansion we get

$$\begin{aligned} & G(Q_{m+1}^n, Q^{n-1}, Q^{n-2}, X) = 0 \\ \Leftrightarrow & G(Q_m^n + \Delta Q, Q^{n-1}, Q^{n-2}, X) = 0 \\ \Leftrightarrow & G(Q_m^n, Q^{n-1}, Q^{n-2}, X) + \frac{\partial G}{\partial Q_m^n} \Delta Q = 0 \\ \Leftrightarrow & \frac{\partial G}{\partial Q_m^n} \Delta Q = -G(Q_m^n, Q^{n-1}, Q^{n-2}, X) \\ \Leftrightarrow & \left(\frac{3V}{2\Delta t} + \frac{\partial R}{\partial Q_m^n} \right) \Delta Q = \\ & = -R(Q_m^n, X) \\ & - \frac{3V}{2\Delta t} Q_m^n + \frac{2V}{\Delta t} Q_m^{n-1} - \frac{1V}{2\Delta t} Q_m^{n-2} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

System (7) can for example be solved using an explicit 5-stage Runge-Kutta scheme, where the matrix sum $\left(\frac{3V}{2\Delta t} + \frac{\partial R}{\partial Q_m^n} \right)$ is substituted by a block-Jacobi preconditioning matrix.

During or after the time-dependent solution of the system of equations, i.e. the computation of the flow vector at each time step n , $(Q^1, Q^2, \dots, Q^{n-1}, Q^n, \dots, Q^N)$, an objective or constraint function of interest, such as lift and drag of an airfoil, the efficiency or capacity of a turbine or efficiency and pressure ratio of a compressor stage, can be calculated. This scalar function J , describing the objective or constraint of interest, can thus be formulated mathematically as

$$\begin{aligned} J &= \frac{1}{T_p} \int_0^{T_p} \tilde{J}(Q(t), X, a) dt \\ &\simeq \frac{1}{T_p} \sum_{n=1}^N \tilde{J}^n(Q^n, X, a). \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

This means we are interested in the mean value J of \tilde{J} over a certain period of time T_p . In gradient-based optimization we need the gradient of J w.r.t. the design variables α in order to minimize (or maximize) J . Developing the gradient in a straightforward way, we get

$$\frac{\partial J}{\partial \alpha} = \frac{\partial J}{\partial Q} \frac{\partial Q}{\partial \alpha} + \frac{\partial J}{\partial X} \frac{\partial X}{\partial \alpha} + \frac{\partial J}{\partial a}. \quad (9)$$

Whether we choose to calculate directly $\frac{\partial J}{\partial \alpha}$ or use the expansion of equation 9 (which means calculating $\frac{\partial Q}{\partial \alpha}$ and $\frac{\partial X}{\partial \alpha}$ first) we cannot avoid perturbing the design space for every single component of the matrix to calculate the gradient. The cost of that is the product of a primal calculation times the dimension of the design space. The fact that the cost of the primal calculation for large scale unsteady problems can be in the range of days and the dimension of a realistic design space can be of order 10^2 and more makes the forward calculation of gradients prohibitive.

Therefore we will expand the objective function of eq. (8) as follows:

$$J_{aug} = J + \Lambda^T G + \Psi^T R_m. \quad (10)$$

throughout the code. It is not intended to give a detailed view of the code but to set the ground for the next section (4).

In the primal code, the flux-contribution to the residual $R(Q_m^n, X)$ of eq. (7) are calculated through a series of operations. For the adjoint code, Tapenade [21], a tool for generating source code by Algorithmic Differentiation (AD), is used in order to obtain $\frac{\partial R}{\partial Q^n} \Lambda^n$ for eq. (18) and a short explanation of the procedure to obtain this term is given below:

Assume that there is a (primal) piece of code with I as input and O as output. Tapenade (when using the reverse mode, see [21]) is capable of producing a new piece of code where $\left[\frac{\partial O}{\partial I}\right]^T \kappa$ is also computed (κ is a user chosen vector). Assume now that we have a series of operations:

$$W \xrightarrow{a} X \xrightarrow{b} Y \xrightarrow{c} Z$$

or i.e. $Z = Z(Y(X(W)))$. Assume also that we want to calculate $\left[\frac{\partial Z}{\partial W}\right]^T \kappa$ (where κ is a vector). Since we do not want to apply Tapenade to the entire sequence to reduce the complexity of the generated code, we expand as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\frac{\partial Z}{\partial W}\right]^T \kappa \\ = & \left[\frac{\partial Z}{\partial Y} \frac{\partial Y}{\partial X} \frac{\partial X}{\partial W}\right]^T \kappa \\ = & \underbrace{\left[\frac{\partial X}{\partial W}\right]^T}_{a} \underbrace{\left[\frac{\partial Y}{\partial X}\right]^T}_{b} \underbrace{\left[\frac{\partial Z}{\partial Y}\right]^T}_{c} \kappa \end{aligned}$$

We have shown that in order to obtain the desired gradient, the sequence of the operations should be reversed. Similarly, in the flow solver, a sequence of operations is needed to obtain the residual R using the flow Q as an input. In order to obtain $\left[\frac{\partial R}{\partial Q}\right]^T \Lambda$, these operations should be reversed after AD is applied to every single one of them. $\left[\frac{\partial J}{\partial Q}\right]^T$ is calculated in a similar way, by applying AD to the bits of code that calculate the objective function using the flow vector as input.

4 ROTOR-STATOR INTERFACE

For turbomachinery applications, an interface that connects the stationary stator with the rotating rotor mesh is required for multi-row calculations, which is typically called a sliding plane. Firstly, the formulation of this sliding plane method that is implemented in the primal will be reviewed and then its adjoint counterpart will be formulated.

Meshes for the stator and rotor rows are generated in such a way that they exhibit a one-cell overlap between two adjacent rows (Fig. 1). Thus, two contact

surfaces are created, on which the solution variables between stationary and rotating zones are interpolated. The inner/donor surface of one row is attached to the

Figure 1: One-cell overlap of adjacent rows' meshes on radial cut. Red: inner/donor surface. Green: outer/receiver surface.

outer/receiver surface of the other row and vice versa. Flow variables are interpolated from the nodes of the donor face to the ones of the receiver face. Since the code is working on each row independently in a relative frame of reference, we need to perform the interpolation in a universal absolute frame. The following three steps are necessary:

1. Transformation to the absolute frame of reference

$$Q^0 T^{abs} = Q^1 \quad (19)$$

where T^{abs} is the transformation matrix to the absolute frame of reference.

2. Interpolation of values from donor to receiver nodes

A search is performed to locate receiver nodes that lie inside donor faces. Then, weight coefficients (w_i) are calculated based on the distance between the receiver and the donors (Fig. 2).

$$w_i = \frac{d_i}{\sum_{j=1}^{\sigma} d_j} \quad (20)$$

where σ is the number of nodes of the corresponding face and d_i is the distance between receiver and donors.

We then can calculate the interpolated values using

$$\sum_{j=1}^{\sigma} w_j Q_j^1 = Q^2 \quad (21)$$

3. Transformation back to the relative frame of reference

$$Q^2 T^{rel} = Q^3 \quad (22)$$

Figure 2: Node interpolation on axial cut. Red: inner/donor nodes. Green: outer/receiver nodes.

The method can be viewed as a sequence of operations on the flow variables ($Q^0 \rightarrow Q^1 \rightarrow Q^2 \rightarrow Q^3$) which is similar to the one introduced in section (3). In order to use the method in the adjoint code, we need to apply AD to the different steps and reverse them. Thus we perform the following calculations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left[\frac{\partial R}{\partial Q^0} \right]^T \Lambda = \\
 & = \underbrace{\left[\frac{\partial Q^1}{\partial Q^0} \right]^T}_{1} \underbrace{\left[\frac{\partial Q^2}{\partial Q^1} \right]^T}_{2} \underbrace{\left[\frac{\partial Q^3}{\partial Q^2} \right]^T}_{3} \underbrace{\left[\frac{\partial R^1}{\partial Q^3} \right]^T}_{\Lambda}. \quad (23)
 \end{aligned}$$

5 EXAMPLE TESTCASES

Two representative turbomachinery testcases are chosen to demonstrate the unsteady adjoint solver and the adjoint sliding plane functionality in this paragraph. Obtaining the unsteady adjoint flow is the main target of those applications. Full optimization cycles and evaluation of the optimized results is the objective of future work.

5.1 Turbine Nozzle Guide Vane

The first testcase involves the first stator of a High Pressure Turbine (HPT - Fig. 3a). The 3D mesh of a single passage consists of ~ 1 million nodes (Fig. 3b, 3c). The following boundary conditions are employed:

- inflow: prescribed total pressure, total temperature, flow angles and turbulence profile
- outflow: prescribed static pressure profile
- viscous wall treatment for all gas-washed surfaces
- periodicity treatment for periodic boundary conditions

Figure 3: Geometry and mesh

Figure 4: Static pressure on surface and velocity magnitude streamlines

For the primal calculations a time period of duration $T_p = 1.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$ s is selected consisting of 128 time-steps. The simulation loops over the period until periodicity of the flow is observed. Once converged, a vortex-shedding appears downstream of the trailing edge. Even though the unsteadiness is not obvious in Fig. 5.1, it can be seen in Fig. 5a, 5b, where relative velocity is shown at two different time-steps or Fig. 6a, 6b, where one mach number isosurface is plotted.

Figure 5: Relative velocity vector near trailing edge at two different time-steps on radial cut at mid height

Figure 8: Adjoint density isosurface at three different time-steps

Figure 6: Mach number isosurface near trailing edge at two different time-steps

The unsteady adjoint solver can now be executed based on what has been described in section 2. The objective function that is used for demonstration purposes is reduced mass flow at the inflow boundary. This quantity is very important for turbine nozzle guide vanes, since it sets the operating point of the whole engine. Firstly, the flow adjoint vector Λ is computed. Different variables of the adjoint vector are shown in Figs. 7 and 8 at different time-steps.

Figure 7: Adjoint velocity magnitude at four different time-steps on radial cut

We can also compute the more visually intuitive surface sensitivities $\frac{\partial J}{\partial X_s}$. They indicate sensitive areas on the gas-washed surfaces and provide the direction of surface modification (inwards/outwards) in order to increase the objective function. The differences between different time-steps are shown in Fig. 9. Note that the differences are small since the unsteadiness is restricted to the trailing edge domain.

Figure 9: Surface sensitivities at different time-steps. Blue: push inwards, red: pull outwards to increase objective

5.2 High Pressure Turbine Stage

The second testcase involves a turbine stage in order to show the sliding plane capabilities developed and presented in this paper. To limit the computational effort, we restrict ourselves to a small slice in radial direction at mid-height of the turbine stage as shown in fig. 10. Nevertheless, the method described in this paper can also be applied to large 3D meshes, which is the topic of future work.

Figure 10: Geometry and mesh of the turbine stage test case

The mesh consists of $\sim 10^5$ nodes. The time period is $T_p = 1.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$ s and 64 time-steps are computed per period.

For visualization, we use repeats of the computational domain: In Fig. 11 the primal flow is shown (note the different position of the rotor row). The wakes are passing through the rotor-stator interface smoothly, which indicates the sliding plane functionality is properly working.

Figure 11: Absolute mach number at two different time-steps on radial cut

Similarly, the adjoint sliding plane functionality is shown in Fig. 12. The objective function in this case is the mass flow at the outflow boundary. Note that the line that appears between the two rows is due to the backward flow of information between receivers and donors, i.e. purely a visualization artefact, and does not affect the adjoint gradient. One can see that the adjoint variables are also continuous across the sliding plane interface, thus indicating visually the proper implementation of the adjoint sliding plane. Additional

numerical validation of the implementation is currently under way and will be presented in subsequent work.

Figure 12: Adjoint density at two different time-steps on radial cut

6 CONCLUSIONS

A time-dependent discrete adjoint capability has been developed and implemented in a 3D URANS solver in order to compute unsteady gradients of chosen objective functions for further use in unsteady optimization. An adjoint sliding plane capability in order to handle multi-row turbomachinery applications has been developed and implemented. The developed code has been demonstrated for two testcases, a high pressure turbine nozzle guide vane and a high pressure turbine stage. The results for those rather simple testcases already indicate the advantages of the adjoint approach for unsteady CFD models, i.e. providing insight into the *unsteady* surface sensitivities can guide the analyst in search for improvements of the shape of the model as well as the use of adjoint-calculated gradients of unsteady functionals for optimization algorithms to for example reduce forcing of turbomachinery blades.

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